

Determining the Attributes Affecting Consumers' Perceptions of the SUV Product Class of the DaimlerChrysler Jeep Cherokee Using the Repertory Grid and the O-A-R Classification

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to determine the key attributes which determine actual and potential consumers' perception of the SUV product class of the DaimlerChrysler Jeep Cherokee (DCJC) and to develop a research instrument that validly and reliably measures the relevant attributes. The definition of the problem is conceptualized utilizing the Object-Attribute-Entity (OAR) classification system outlined by Rossiter (2002) within the Construct definition, Object classification, Attribute classification, Rater identification, Scale formation, and Enumeration and reporting (C-OAR-SE) framework. To generate attributes, the repertory grid technique (Kelly, 1955) is applied. These attributes are further defined by the attribute classification method based on actual and prospective SUV consumer input. The outcome is a research instrument which can be used to assess consumers' perception of the DaimlerChrysler Jeep Cherokee. Both the advantages and disadvantages of this methodology are discussed.

Keywords: Market Research, Empirical Approaches, Development of Research Instruments, Construct Development

Introduction

This research is addressed from the perspective that in order to determine the key attributes which determine consumers' perception of the DaimlerChrysler Jeep Cherokee (DCJC), the correct meaning of the construct must be clearly defined from the start. It is necessary to avoid vague, abstract conceptualizations because they leave too much room for interpretive error (Rossiter, 2002). This paper describes the research problem, "the SUV product class of the DCJC as perceived by consumers" via the Construct definition, Object classification, Attribute classification, Rater identification, Scale formation, and Enumeration and reporting (C-OAR-SE) framework (Rossiter, 2002). The *repertory grid* (Kelly, 1955) method is described and applied to elicit the attributes by actual and prospective SUV consumers for rater-entity classification. The attributes are formulated using *content analysis* by the rater entity based on consumer responses. An analysis and interpretation of the items in the grid by the rater-entity, their resultant attributes and research instrument statements are presented. This is followed by a discussion of the advantages and disadvantages of the methodology and recommendations for further research.

Research Objective:

The goal of this paper is to determine the key attributes which determine actual and prospective consumers' perceptions of the SUV product class of the DaimlerChrysler Jeep Cherokee in particular.

Statement of the Problem:

The problem is the valid and reliable identification of key attributes which determine consumers' perception of the SUV product class, in particular, the DaimlerChrysler Jeep Cherokee. Consumers' perceptions of attributes of DCJC within the SUV product class have yet to be examined using the Object Classification, Attribute Classification, Rater Identification (O-A-R) methodology in the C-OAR-SE framework (Rossiter, 2002). Most measures of consumers' perceptions toward a consumer good such as the SUV product class do not utilize a reliable and valid methodology (eg. in Barnes, 1975). This results from these studies not providing inter-response agreement for the same variable and requires further refinement of the constructs to generate uniform answers. While *measurement error* exists in any study (Hair, 2006), the research is improved by finding ways to reduce it (Rossiter, 2002). In other words, the researcher needs to be sure that the items comprising the attribute are all oriented toward a single underlying dimension: in this case, the key attributes that determine the actual and prospective consumers' perceptions toward the SUV product class of the DCJC in particular.

Furthermore, in these studies the researchers invalidly impose their view of what the perceived product attributes were rather than allowing it to evolve from consumer interviews. Contrary to standard methodology, researchers have developed research instruments based on intuitive judgments rather than applying consumer supplied attributes (eg., in SERVQUAL, Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1988 and in the Market Orientation scale, Narver & Slater, 1990). The process of using the *repertory grid technique*, on the other hand, enables the consumer to articulate his or her own understanding of the world and reveals what consumers think about a product such as SUVs without superimposing the researcher's prejudice (eg., in Johansson & Thorelli, 1985). This also improves the reliability the research.

This study extends the *repertory grid* to actual and prospective consumers' perceptions of SUVs because it offers a powerful way of quantifying people's attitudes, feelings, and perceptions (Easterby-Smith, 1996). This also contrasts with conventional empirical approaches, such as factor analysis which often classify people in the researcher's schema of the world and may provide inconsistent inter-item descriptions of the attributes (eg. in Taylor & Baker's, 1994 measure, and in more than one in 10 of the scales in Bearden, Netemeyer, and Mobley, 1993, *Handbook of Marketing Scales*). This research attempts to rectify some of these methodological issues, and expands the theoretical and empirical work on the application of O-A-R, as well as demonstrating the usefulness of *the repertory grid technique*, as applied to the development of a research instrument to measure consumers' perceptions.

Methodology

The construct under study is defined as "the key attributes affecting actual and prospective consumers' perceptions of the SUV product class of the DCJC." This study utilizes the O-A-R classification method proposed by Rossiter (2002) to disaggregate the construct into its object, attributes and rater entity. This methodology is useful because it is comprised of a comprehensive disaggregation of all the relevant elements related to the construct under study. This O-A-R methodology also provides a standardized, comprehensive format that ensures the validity and reliability of this study as well as being readily applicable to other such studies.

The method used to identify the key attributes which influence consumers' perceptions of the DCJC is the *repertory grid technique*. The *repertory grid technique* is a tool through which we can attempt to uncover and formally represent how individuals construct their world. In this respect, it can be used to inform the formation of attributes which are classified by the O-A-R classification system and to create a research instrument for the purpose of measuring the key attributes which determine consumers' perceptions of the Jeep Cherokee. The *repertory grid technique* dovetails favorably with the O-A-R classification system because it generates the single or multiple concrete items utilized to define the attribute by the rater-entity. Although the *repertory grid technique* is derived from what was originally utilized as a psychological tool for counseling United State's university students (Kelly, 1955), this study makes an extension and modification of this technique, as has already been done in applications of business related areas such as training and marketing (Stewart, 1981; Easterby-Smith, 1996).

Process of Conducting the Repertory Grid and the O-A-R Classification System

The process of conducting the *repertory grid technique* and inputting its results into the O-A-R classification system is divided into four sequential stages. In Stage one, the focus of the *repertory grid* as defined by the object classification method is identified. In Stage two, the researcher employs the *repertory grid technique* to elicit the words and phrases which in Stage three, are divided into broader categories of attributes by research participants using *content analysis* (Weber, 1985). Stage four is a disaggregation and ratification of attribute categories by inter-judge agreement by rater entities generated in Stage three. The resultant research instrument is derived from the single and multi-part meanings of *abstract formed* and *second-order formed attributes*.

In Stage one, the researcher selected appropriate objects from which to construct the SUV product class of the DCJC test list. Initially, a total of 36 SUV models were selected from *Wards Automotive Report (2006)*, representing at least one model for each of the fourteen best-selling SUV manufacturers. The initial pool of 36 SUV models were evaluated by a pre-test sample, prior to administration of the principal test, to include other models that the pre-test participants recommended. In addition to object ratification, the pre-test sample

provided a preliminary evaluation of the 'SUV Market Research Questionnaire' (Appendix B) used in the *repertory grid technique*.

Sample Selection

Data for the pre-test and principal test was collected from a non-probabilistic, convenience sample through one-on-one, in person interviews' at two service stations in Astoria, New York. In return, for their participation the respondents were offered a *2006 Rand McNally Road Atlas of New York State*. A total of two adults in the pre-test and five adults in the principal test completed the 'SUV Market Research Questionnaire' used in the *repertory grid technique* (Appendix A).

The Pre-test for Object Selection

The pre-test sample provided an evaluation of models to include in the SUV product class of the DCJC test list. This approach is in line with Rossiter (2002) and Simpson and Wilson (1999) who recommend polling the sample to elicit objects to which all participants can relate. The pre-test sample consisted of two adults, both male. Each works in the automobile sector, one as an auto representative and the other as an insurance agent. While they both own an SUV, one described their level of knowledge of SUVs as 'High.' and the other as "Medium."

The pre-test sample further refined the initial pool of 36 SUV models to include other models that they recommended. For example, the pre-test sample suggested that the researcher include The Ford Explorer, Kia Sorento and Honda Pilot as examples of DCJC analogues. After the initial pool of SUVs was further examined by pre-test consumers, the final list of SUV models was constructed (Appendix A). The list was increased from 36 SUV models to 39 SUV models based on this pre-test survey of three representative actual and prospective SUV buyers recommendations.

In Stage two, the five respondents in the principal test were given an 'SUV Market Research Questionnaire' (Appendix B) to elicit his/her responses and to collect background demographic information. The principal test sample consisted of five adults, four males and one female. Their ages ranged between 30 to 50 years of age. The ethnic profile of the principal test sample demographic includes two white, one Hispanic, one Asian and one Egyptian. The occupations of the respondents include a carpenter, store manager, accounting clerk, professor, and building contractor.

In conducting the principal test of the *repertory grid technique*, the names of each of the 39 SUV models were written on a flashcard. Each model in the list of SUVs was identified with its brand name as the object's brand name presented to them on the card and as an SUV in the product class of the DCJC, and as such, was classified as having a single-item concrete meaning in the O-A-R framework. As the collection of SUV models are separate brands and models, yet form a common set of item-parts at a higher categorical level (Rossiter, 2002), the 'SUV product class of the DCJC', was classified as an *abstract collective object*.

The respondent was told that the researcher was conducting academic research for a class on marketing of SUVs, and asked to first complete Section I, 'Demographic Information'. The participants answered questions which ask them to report their age, occupation, gender, ethnicity, and level of knowledge of SUVs. The last three questions of the SUV Market Research Questionnaire, ascertained the actual or prospective SUV ownership status of the respondent, and served as a filter question to ensure that participants were actual and prospective buyers of SUVs of the DCJC product class.

Then, the respondent was asked to scan a set of 39 SUVs, to select a subset which was most familiar to him and then to finally select a subgrouping of three SUVs from the set. The respondents were asked to write three names from the subset of SUVs. Then, they were asked to state "Which two are most similar and which one is most different from the other two?" Then, the respondents were asked to write what makes these two designated SUVs similar? and "What makes the third SUV different from the other two?" on the questionnaire.

After the respondent completed the first grouping of questions, the cards were put back into the pile and reshuffled. Another set of three names of SUVs were randomly selected from the pile, and the respondent wrote responses to the same set of questions. The respondents reiterated this process a total of five times. This procedure was repeated and questions on three SUVs were presented five times.

In Stage three, *content analysis* (Weber, 1985) is provided to describe the outcome of the data generated in the *repertory grid technique*. The researcher, with the assistance of the respondents, selected categories into

which words and phrases fell and labeled the categories as attributes. The respondents communicated with the researcher by email in regards to how the pool of words and phrases would develop into attributes after they reviewed the total list. In generating the attributes, it was important that the researcher did not impose her perspective on research participants' responses, and allowed the attributes to emerge from the articulation of the consumers' recommendation. In doing this, the researcher made sure that the target-rater's words and short phrases only applied to the attributes they recommended. In addition, the words and phrases which were mentioned the most frequently in their attribute category, as well as had minimal overlap with other words and phrases, were the ones that were chosen to be included in the attribute.

The respondent developed the attribute of "appearance" by reference to the items "best looks," "good shape", "nice shape", "look the same" "boring", "ugly," "poor design," "no appeal to it," "not for show," and "box shape." The words and phrases which made-up the "appearance" attribute comprised a quarter of all responses. It was ascertained that consumers make significant distinctions in terms of appearance and that appearance is an important part of the consumer evaluation process. Ten responses out of fifty-five were generated related to the attribute of "performance". The components used to describe performance include "horsepower," "drives well," "versatile," "lasts forever," "reliable," "durable," "nice ride," "sport," "performs all weather," "4X4", "all wheel power", "an all out off-roader," "for the road, not the trail," "good for the winter," and "lean and mean."

"Comfortable interior" "rugged interior" and "spacious" are being used in the same way to describe what the consumer designated as the attribute "interior". These items comprised 11% of all responses. Consumers from the sample group also used the title "power" to describe the attribute which consisted of the words "towing capacity," "good powerplant", "nice drivetrain," and "decent power." These phrases comprised 11% of all responses. The residual words and phrases were categorized by respondents to represent "size" (9%), "mechanical quality" (7%), "comfort" (4%), and "solidity" (2%).

As *content analysis* typically includes inter-judge agreement (Weber, 1985) and judgment of the object-attribute by rater entity is an inseparable part of the construct under study (Rossiter, 2002), in Stage four, the rater entity is used to judge the meaning of the attributes after the items are categorized in Stage 3. These multiple judges are identified and classified, as required by the rater-entity classification method of O-A-R, as a sample of owners and prospective buyers of a SUV in the product class of the DCJC.

The individuals who served as a rater entity in the group of SUV owners and prospective buyers were suggested to the researcher by colleagues, friends and relatives. The researcher explained to the rater entity that their judgment on these items and attributes were used for marketing purposes of the SUVs. After being briefed on the objectives of the study, the individuals agreed to attentively give two hours of their time to complete the process of ratifying the attributes

The rater entity classified the attributes into *formed abstract attributes* and *second-order abstract attributes*. The *formed attributes* have components with a single-concrete meaning and are easier to work with in terms of quickly identifying a single concrete component meaning (Rossiter, 2002). The *second-order formed attributes*, have components with multiple meanings and are classified as *first-order formed attributes* (Rossiter, 2002). The process of evaluating the concrete component meanings of the *first-order formed attributes* added another phase of inter-judge agreement. For example, the *second-order formed attribute* "performance" has a multi-part component or *first order formed attribute* "durable" which is broken-down into "long-life", "resists deterioration", and "consistently performs" and their corresponding concrete meanings. When at least two-thirds of the sample group approved the meanings of *the first-order* and *second order formed attributes* such attributes were accepted for inclusion in the final questionnaire as measures of consumers' perceptions of SUVs.

The process entailed email delivery of a rating sheet asking the rater entities to disaggregate the attribute formed in the *content analysis* of Stage 3 into components. In order to achieve inter-rater agreement on the meaning of the selected attributes, the researcher asked the rater entities, three in this case, to write down the attribute's component meanings of the various attributes. Where there was inter-rater agreement the attributes were viewed as fully defined and certified, but where there was disagreement in the meanings of the components the rater entities were asked to discuss their differing concepts, over email, of the component of a particular attribute until a consensus was met.

Results

A total of 55 words and phrases were elicited from the interviewees in *the repertory grid technique*. The items generated by the repertory grid technique were summarized using *content analysis* (Table 1). The final set of nine attributes which emerged from *content analysis* include the attribute categories "performance", "economy," "power," "interior," "size," "mechanical quality", "comfort" and "solidity." The frequency count shows that respondents generated fourteen words and phrases for "appearance," ten phrases for "performance", seven phrases for "economy", six phrases for "interior," six phrases for "power", five phrases for "size", four phrases for "mechanical quality," two phrases for "comfort" and one phrase for the "attribute" solidity. The words and phrases related to appearance, accounted for a quarter of all items reported.

The major *formed attributes* are "power", "interior", "size", "mechanical quality", and "comfort" (Table 2). There was very substantial inter-rater agreement among the three judges with respect to the *formed attributes*, providing confidence that the meaning of the attributes enjoys substantial agreement among target-raters as well. The major *second-order formed attributes* are "appearance," "performance," "economy" and (4) "solidity" (Table 3). There was also a high level of inter-rater agreement strengthening the reliability of the *second-order formed attributes*.

The outcome of the inter-judge rating and classification of is a research instrument (Appendix C) which includes the single and multi-item measures of consumers' perceptions of the aforementioned attributes. The order of multiple items across *formed attribute* components and single-item meanings are randomized (Rosssiter, 2002). In order for the attribute to be properly constituted, the concrete meaning of all attributes which received at least two-third inter-rater agreement are present on the research instrument. The statements in each *formed attribute* and *second-order formed attribute* category reflect perceptions related to the following attributes of "the SUV product class of the DCJC:" "power," "interior," "size," "mechanical quality," "comfort," "appearance," "performance," "economy," and "solidity."

Consumers from the rater entity sample group helped optimize and provided confirmational input in regards to formulating the statements which reflect their corresponding attributes and component meanings. When the rater entities did not have more than one-third shared agreement on the single-item meanings of the components, they were not included in the final pool of statements selected for the development of statements in the research instrument. By focusing on the research participants own expressions, the researcher was also able to minimize the researcher's bias in interpreting descriptions.

The instructions on the research instrument direct the interviewees to rate each statement on a 0-to-5 *Edwards Delight Scale* (www.strategicvision.com). The five points of the *Edwards Delight Scale* include the following: "Delightful" equals 5, "Excellent" equals 4, "Satisfactory" equals 3, "Unsatisfactory" equals 2, and "Failure" equals 1. According to Webster's Dictionary, "Delightful" means to take one beyond their expectations and satisfy him/her completely while "Excellent" refers to a highly satisfactory satisfaction but does not achieve total satisfaction, "Satisfactory" connotes an acceptable level but one which falls short of excellence, "Unsatisfactory" connotes a substantial dissatisfaction but short of being a failure, and "Failure" connotes the failure of a vehicle characteristic to perform as intended and a severe feature shortcoming. The scale also included a separate "don't know" category.

The structure of the questionnaire is such that it can easily be adapted to measure the perceptions of actual and prospective SUV consumers to not only DCJC, but other SUVs of the product class of the DCJC. That is, other brands could be substituted for DCJC as the focal object.

Discussion

This study demonstrates the usefulness of utilizing the O-A-R classification *and repertory grid technique* in terms of problem definition, data generation and research instrument development. While there are many positive aspects to this methodology, it has limitations as well which are acknowledged.

The method of disaggregating the construct into its O-A-R classification is a highly useful one because it provides a clarity derived from its clear presentation, which has the potential for cross-study utilization that ensures reliability and validity. While the *repertory grid technique* assists in generating the attributes' components and constituent parts that are used in the research instrument, the O-A-R classification system

makes it possible to provide valid and reliable measures of the attributes through inter-rater entity agreement. The *repertory grid technique* is also innovative in that it looks at objects from the standpoint of the consumer rather than the researcher. Both the O-A-R and the *repertory grid technique* methods are beyond the traditional limited methodologies discussed above and they represent a paradigm shift in that these methods do not rely on traditional exploratory factor analysis.

In using the *repertory grid technique* in this study, the participant is asked to identify and label some way in which three SUVs are similar yet different from the designated third in the SUV product class of the DCJC. Another approach would be to evaluate pre-constructed groupings of three SUVs. The grouping of three SUVs would be comprised of the Jeep Cherokee and its direct competitors. This approach more directly sheds light on Jeep Cherokee's strengths and weaknesses, and the attributes affecting consumers' perception of Jeep's position relative to its competitors. The *repertory grid method* in this study could also be expanded to include as elements non-SUVs in order to obtain some diversity regarding vehicles in all the aspects of owning, driving and fuel economy.

An improvement to the methodology in the demographic section of the questionnaire used in the *repertory grid technique* would be to define exactly what do "Excellent", "Fair," "Poor", or "Non-Existent" level of knowledge of SUVs mean since what one person believes to be an excellent level of knowledge may be a low level of knowledge for another. However, for the purpose of this study, this information is used to provide a rough approximation of the participants as active rather than passive users of the knowledge related to SUVs. Although the initial sample was carefully chosen for knowledge of SUVs, it turned out by the end of the study that some raters were much more knowledgeable than others. To compensate for the disparate knowledge levels of the rater entities, the data could be weighted with the highest weight assigned to the most knowledgeable and the lowest weight assigned to the least knowledgeable. The validity of the survey could be increased by skewing the results in the direction of the most knowledgeable.

One drawback of the study is that a sample size of only five individuals was not adequate to represent the large universe of prospective and actual SUV buyers. Some of the useful sample dimensions would include urban versus rural residency, income level, married versus single, driving for commuting for business versus leisure driving, and first-time buyer versus repeat buyer of a SUV. In order to increase the applicability of the study it would be necessary to increase the size of the sample group while assuming that it included the aforementioned characteristics. In line with standard research methods, it would also be more effective to use a random sample rather than the herein utilized convenience sample. Specifically, a random group is far more insightful than a convenience group since one can extrapolate a scientifically chosen random sample to represent the entire class of individuals covered by the study.

The inter-rater agreement classification process is useful because as a multiple-input process, it is more useful than relying on the intuitive judgments that would be used in finding uni-dimensionality in factor analysis of an attribute. One disadvantage of this process is that it is difficult to identify the owners and prospective buyers of SUVs without having access to an SUV dealer or manufacturer. Secondly, there is the important challenge of finding some way to motivate the inter-raters to complete the inter-rater judgment process because it involves many hours of attentive work which requires some incentive, presumably monetary. Financially compensating the rater entities would entail high expense. Funds would presumably come from the universities and the manufacturers' market research divisions.

One of the great challenges of developing the research instrument is that in the writing of the statements many of the components used to represent the attribute had vague meanings. That is, many research participants were not likely to interpret the questions consistently, reducing the reliability and validity of the instrument. Developing statements for the research instrument by breaking the attribute into *abstract formed* and *second order attributes* with single concrete meanings helped clarify otherwise vague and confusing words.

While the process of comparing similarities and differences amongst a group of three SUVs produced the contrasting pole of both negative and positive reactions, rendering the use of a semantic differential bipolar scale, the researcher exercised her discretion to use a uni-polar scale instead. This is because a bipolar scale would treat a single dimension as having two rather than one attribute. A uni-polar scale, on the other hand, would detect the presence of an attribute, as opposed to its absence.

While the 0-to-5 *Edwards Delight Scale* is a uni-polar survey that is widely used in the automobile/SUV market, it presumes a level of satisfaction that can only be answered from ownership of an SUV. For prospective buyers' responses on the characteristics of the SUV are inevitably more superficial than actual SUV owners because their judgments are based on a more intuitive rather than actual experience. However, the scale still uncovers their underlying perceptions as the attributes are relevant to their understanding of SUVs.

There are an infinite number of attributes related to the product's characteristic and the emotional responses consumers have to SUVs. This is especially true in regards to SUVs because they are large, complex vehicles and a relatively new product class. While the attributes in this study are not comprehensive, they touch on many of the larger areas of marketing SUVs given the small number of rater-entities. The list of potential formed and second order attributes is extremely large and beyond the scope of this study. While the attributes are disaggregated into their major constituent parts, it is acknowledged that there are many constituent parts beyond those generated in this study. To uncover all of the possible multiple and single items meanings of the attributes, it is important to identify the appropriate individuals involved in the SUV product. Underlying the soundness of the study is its empirical approach which by traditional empirical standards involves direct participation of SUV consumers as opposed to a theoretical deduction approach which would have reflected substantially the prejudices of the researcher.

Recommendations for Further Research

It is the hope of the researcher that other researchers would look at the components and constituents which comprise the object-attributes-rater entity of this study related to attributes affecting actual and consumers' perception of the SUV product class of the DCJC and in doing a similar study related to the attribute of the object by the target rater, use this study as a guide. Further studies should expand the sample beyond five to at least twenty-five to see if the conclusions are applicable beyond the sample of target raters and rater entities that originally judged the attributes, components and constituents. The next step would be to study how mathematically intensive factor analysis, and other approaches could be used to complement rather than impede the methodology presented in this paper to generate even more significant findings.

Conclusions

In summary, the study identifies the key attributes affecting consumers' perceptions of the SUV product class of the DCJC. By clarifying the object-attribute-rater entity of the construct and using the *repertory grid technique* to elicit attributes, the study provides a systematic approach that can be utilized in many market research assignments. Its use will lead to more effective marketing of the product studied by introducing a higher level of rigor to what has traditionally been an *ad hoc* approach to conceptualizing constructs. The process was also, for the researcher, a highly educational one and improved the researcher's abilities and knowledge of methods used to measure constructs.

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Table 1
Frequency Count and Categorization of Repertory Grid Words and Phrases into Attributes

Attribute	Items Mentioned	Total Number of Items Mentioned	% of Total
APPEARANCE	Best looks (1) Good shape (1) Nice shape (1) Look the same (3) Boring (1) Ugly (2) Poor design (1) No appeal to it (1) Not for show (1) Box shape (1)	14	25%
PERFORMANCE	Horsepower (1) Drives well (1) Versatile (2) Lasts forever (1) Reliable (1) Durable (1) Nice ride (1) Sporty (1) Performs all weather (1) 4X4 (1) All wheel power (1) An all out off-roader (1) For the road, not the trail (1) Good for the winter (1) Lean and mean (1)	10	18%
ECONOMY	Fuel economy (2) Is good on gas (1) Horrible on gas (2) Too expensive (1) Gas Guzzler (1)	7	13%
POWER	Towing capacity (2) Good Powerplant (1) Nice Drivetrain (1) Decent power 2	6	11%
INTERIOR	Comfortable Interior (2) Rugged Interior (1) Spacious (3)	6	11%
SIZE	Big (3) Can see over people (1) Small (1)	5	9%
MECHANICAL QUALITY	High quality parts (1) Breaks down often 2 Responds well to upgrades (1)	4	7%
COMFORT	Riding comfort (2)	2	4%
SOLIDITY	Well put together (1)	1	2%
TOTAL ITEMS		55	100%

Table 2

Formed Attributes of the SUV Product Class of the Jeep Cherokee

Formed Attribute	Component	Single-item concrete component	Reliability Estimate (i.e. Inter-rater agreement amongst 3 judges)
POWER	Size of engine	Number of cylinders	3-out-of-3, 100%
	Towing capacity	Trailer towing capacity	3-out-of-3, 100%
INTERIOR	Leg Interior	Roominess for legs	3-out-of-3, 100%
	Cargo Interior	Capacity for cargo	3-out-of-3, 100%
	Passenger capacity	The number of people who can sit comfortably inside	3-out-of-3, 100%
SIZE	Length	Front to back length (feet)	3-out-of-3, 100%
	Width	Door-to-door (inches)	1 out of 3, 33%
	Height	Ground to top of roof (in inches)	3-out-of-3, 100%
MECHANICAL QUALITY	Engine	Number of cylinders	3-out-of-3, 100%
	Brakes	Ability to stop	3-out-of-3, 100%
	Battery	Supply of electricity	3-out-of-3, 100%
COMFORT	Front seat comfort	Driver's seat	3-out-of-3, 100%
	Rear seat comfort	Passengers' seat	3-out-of-3, 100%
	Staying warm in the winter	Heater	3-out-of-3, 100%
	Staying cool in the summer	Air conditioner	3-out-of-3, 100%

Table 3

Second-Order Formed Attributes of the SUV Product Class of the Jeep Cherokee

<i>Formed Attribute (second-order)</i>	<i>Formed Attribute (first-order)</i>	<i>First-Order Component</i>	<i>One Item Measure of the First-Order Component</i>	<i>Reliability Estimates (Inter-rater Agreement amongst 3 judges)</i>
APPEARANCE	Body	Traditional	Box-like contours	3-out-of-3, 100%
		Modern	Round contours	3-out-of-3, 100%
	Front of the car	Headlights	Front lights	3-out-of-3, 100%
		The opening at the front of the vehicle to allow air to flow in to cool the engine	Grille	3-out-of-3, 100%
	Back of the car	Rear design	Backlights	3-out-of-3, 100%
PERFORMANCE	Durability	Long life	Lasts a long time	1-out-of-3, 33%
		Resists deterioration	The need to replace parts	3-out-of-3, 100%
	Reliability	Consistently performs	The ability for the engine to start-up	3-out-of-3, 100%
		Performance in all weather conditions	The ability to run in the winter	3-out-of-3, 100%
	Speed	Has good pick up	The ability to accelerate promptly for passing other vehicles	2-out-of-3, 66%
		Highway speed	The ability to drive fast consistently on long highway distances	1 out of 3 agreement, 33%
ECONOMY	Cost	Affordable to buy	Expense to buy	3-out-of-3, 100%
		Affordable to maintain	Expense to maintain	3-out-of-3, 100%
		Fuel Efficiency	Mileage per gallon	3-out-of-3, 100%
SOLIDITY	Resistant to minor collisions	The front bumpers protects the vehicle from minor impacts	The ability to withstand collision without severe damage to the vehicle's frame in the front	3-out-of-3, 100%
		The back bumpers protect the vehicle from minor impacts	The ability to withstand severe damage to the vehicle's frame in the back	3-out-of-3, 100%

Appendix A

The Repertory Grid Test List

Acura MDX	Hummer H2	Mercury Mariner
Audi Q7	Hummer H3	Mitsubishi Endeavor
BMW X3	Hyundai Santa Fe	Nissan Pathfinder
Buick Rainier	Infiniti FX35	Pontiac Torrent
Cadillac Escalade	Isuzu Ascender	Porsche Cayenne
Chevrolet Suburban	Jeep Cherokee	Saab 9-7x
Chevrolet Tahoe	Jeep Wrangler	Saturn VUE
Dodge Durango	Kia Sorento	Subaru Tribeca
Ford Explorer	Land Rover Range	Suzuki Grand Vitara
GMC Yukon	Lexus GX470	Toyota 4Runner
Honda CR-V	Lincoln Navigator	Toyota Highlander
Honda Pilot	Mazda Tribute	Volkswagen Touareg
Hummer H1	Mercedes-Benz M-Class	Volvo XC90

French list

Acura MDX	Hummer H2	Mercury Mariner
Audi Q7/Q5	Hummer H3	Mitsubishi Endeavor
BMW X3	Hyundai Santa Fe	Nissan Pathfinder/X-Trail (2014)
Buick Rainier	Infiniti FX35	Pontiac Torrent
Cadillac Escalade	Isuzu Ascender	Porsche Cayenne (2014)
Chevrolet Suburban	Jeep Cherokee	Saab 9-7x
Chevrolet Tahoe	Jeep Wrangler	Saturn VUE
Dodge Durango	Kia Sorento	Subaru Tribeca/Forester
Ford Explorer	Land Rover Range	Suzuki Grand Vitara/2015
GMC Yukon	Lexus GX470	Toyota 4Runner (RAV4)
Honda CR-V	Lincoln Navigator	Toyota Highlander
Honda Pilot	Mazda Tribute	Volkswagen Touareg (2014)
Hummer H1	Mercedes-Benz M-Class/Classe GLS	Volvo XC90 (2014)

Source:

Appendix B

SUV Market Research Questionnaire

I am conducting academic research on marketing of SUVs (Sports Utility Vehicles). I would be greatly appreciative if you could take a few minutes to share your thoughts.

Section I: Demographic Information

Directions: Please complete the following demographic information before completing Section II, 'The Five SUV Triads.'

1. Age (years): _____
2. Current Occupation: _____
3. Your Gender: _____ Male _____ Female
4. What is your ethnicity? _____ White
_____ Black
_____ Latin
_____ Asian
_____ Other
5. How would you describe your level of SUV knowledge? (Check one)
_____ Excellent
_____ Fair
_____ Poor
_____ Non-Existent
6. Do you own/lease an SUV?
_____ Yes
_____ No
_____ Maybe (If 'No', then proceed to Question 7)
- 6a. If you own/lease an SUV, would you purchase/lease another SUV?
_____ Yes
_____ No
_____ Maybe
7. If you don't own a SUV, are you planning to purchase/lease one?.
_____ Yes
_____ No

Section II: SUV Grouping

Directions: Select any three SUVs from the cards that you are familiar with. Please provide answers to the questions below for each grouping of 3 SUVs you select from the list of cards. After completing the first set of questions, select another group of three SUVs that you are familiar with and repeat the same questions provided below.

Grouping 1

Names of SUVs selected:

Which two are more similar and which one is most different?

What makes these two similar?

What makes this one different from the other two?

Grouping 2

Names of SUVs selected:

Which two are more similar and which one is most different?

What makes these two similar?

What makes this one different from the other two?

Grouping 3

Names of SUVs selected:

Which two are more similar and which one is most different?

What makes these two similar?

What makes this one different from the other two?

Grouping 4

Names of SUVs selected:

Which two are more similar and which one is most different?

What makes these two similar?

What makes this one different from the other two?

Grouping 5

Names of SUVs selected:

Which two are more similar and which one is most different?

What makes these two similar?

What makes this one different from the other two?

Thank you for your participation.

Appendix B

Research Instrument

An Index for Consumers' Perceptions of Sports Utility Vehicle

Please rate each statement on the following scale of 0-to-5 to indicate the degree to which s/he perceived an attribute to exist for the given SUV. Circle the number which corresponds with your answer on this sheet.

Definitions of Labels:

- Delightful (5): Means to take one beyond satisfaction.
- Excellent (4): Refers to a highly satisfactory satisfaction but does not achieve total satisfaction.
- Satisfactory (3): Connotes an acceptable level but one which falls short of excellence.
- Unsatisfactory (2): Connotes a substantial dissatisfaction but one short of being a failure.
- Failure (1): The failure of a vehicle characteristic to perform as intended and a severe feature shortcoming.

Name of SUV that is being evaluated against its features listed below: "Jeep Cherokee"

	Failure	Unsatisfactory	Satisfaction	Excellent	Delightful	
POWER						
1. The number of cylinders are (a)	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
2. The trailer towing capacity is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
INTERIOR						
3. The capacity for cargo is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
4. The roominess for legs is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
5. The number of people who can sit in it (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
SIZE						
6. The ground to top of roof height is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
7. The front to back length (feet) is (a)	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
MECHANICAL QUALITY						
8. The ability to stop is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
9. The number of cylinders is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
10. The supply of electricity is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
COMFORT						
11. The driver's seat is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
12. The heater is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
13. The passengers' seat is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
14. The air conditioner is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
APPEARANCE						
15. The front lights are (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
16. The box-like contours are (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
17. The grille is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
18. The backlights are (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
19. The round contours are (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
PERFORMANCE						
20. The need to replace parts is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
21. The ability of the engine to start-up is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
22. The ability to run in the winter is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
23. The ability to accelerate promptly for passing is:	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
ECONOMY						
24. The expense of buying is (a)	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
25. The mileage per gallon is (a)	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
26. The expense of maintaining the (a)	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
SOLID						
27. The ability to withstand collision damage to front is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know
28. The ability to withstand collision damage to back is (a):	1	2	3	4	5	__ Don't know